

Public Knowledge

1. Introduction

Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI)¹ was launched to help institutions and funders better invest in the open technology and systems that research and scholarship rely on. Our work is centered around providing targeted, evidence-based guidance and support to institutions and funders of open infrastructure to help them become wiser about where to invest. The end result: improve the funding and sustainability of the sector, improve the adoption and prevalence of open infrastructure solutions, and provide a counterbalance to commercial entities acting against the interest of the academy.

2. Grant Summary/Abstract

In the attached proposal, “*Catalyzing investment in and adoption of open infrastructure for research*”, we request \$1,000,000 USD over 21 months to support the further development and productization of the Catalog of Open Infrastructure Services (COIs)² and to test models and strategies for sustaining open infrastructure. Funding will be dedicated in large part to providing technical development and leadership support to scale COIs, with additional convening and research support to help grow the uptake and investment in open infrastructure from for-profits, institutions, and other aligned initiatives. This builds on IOI’s existing efforts to provide targeted, evidence-based guidance, analysis, and strategic support to institutions and funders to improve the resourcing, viability, and sustainability for open technologies that underpin research and scholarship. IOI is a fiscally sponsored project of Code for Science & Society, a leading 501(c)3 that supports a portfolio of projects in the public interest technology and research sectors.

3. Reason for the Work

We developed COIs as a means to systematize and streamline the due diligence process for those looking to adopt or better understand the organizational backing for open infrastructure providers. We heard from our Future of Open Scholarship research³ in 2020-21, as well as in our various series of focus groups and interviews⁴ that more information was needed to guide these decisions in an accessible, standardized, values-aligned, and coordinated form. This included governance structure, community engagement, board representation, and funding sources, noting that the time and effort needed, especially for library administrators who have limited time, to examine providers on a case-by-case basis was burdensome and inefficient, particularly without standards for how this information is described and reported. Across stakeholders interviewed as part of our research, we heard many share similar sentiments regarding the difficulty, burdensome nature of due diligence, and absence of a standard approach to the process. This often led to decisions to adopt commercial offerings due to expediency and efficiency to meet the needs of the research community, as well as the ease found with commercial companies’ abilities to navigate often complex institutional procurement and approval systems. While we don’t anticipate COIs being able to address all of the challenges and blocking issues that exist in increasing adoption of open infrastructure, stakeholder have also surfaced additional points for consideration including pre-existing relationships with institutions (where a vendor may already be approved in procurement and billing systems), dedicated user services and implementation support, clear cost estimates for implementation and maintenance, and availability of service level and other legal agreements that a vendor could reach with a library or institution’s legal counsel.

In January 2022, we launched the initial prototype of a Catalog of Open Infrastructure Services (COIs) with the support of the Mellon Foundation. COIs is designed as a resource for funders, users, and other interested stakeholders looking to make informed decisions about the open infrastructure services available for research and scholarship. We want to support the ongoing conversations about important issues of financing, governance, and administration of open infrastructure by advancing our mutual understanding of key issues in providing important services and building an ecosystem of reliable, resilient, and community-driven infrastructure supporting a global community of researchers, scholars, and other users. We are also proud to announce that in order to achieve these goals, we are including new assessment criteria for open infrastructures that go beyond typical market-driven indicators. These

¹ <https://investinopen.org>

² <https://investinopen.org/catalog/>

³ <https://investinopen.org/research/future-of-open-scholarship/>

⁴ <https://investinopen.org/blog/the-costs-of-open-infrastructure-conversations-with-providers-funders-and-institutions/>

include, but are not limited to, deeper assessments of governance structures, accessibility considerations (e.g. bandwidth and connectivity concerns, languages available), affordability, embeddedness in a community, reliability and delivery of services (e.g. dependencies, maintenance, implementation support), and interdependence. More on these additional criteria can be found in our Funding Framework⁵, which is a living, breathing document under active development and consultation with IOI stakeholders.

We designed this web-based application to test key assumptions about what information was needed to describe and promote open infrastructure services among key funders. Through targeted engagement, user interviews, and listening sessions with a diverse and global community of potential users, we have identified and validated the value of COIs in addressing key information gaps for funders and budget holders, as well as driving change in infrastructure service providers' governance and information disclosure practices.

At a high level, we sought through recent user interviews conducted by Taimour Azizuddin for IOI to:

- Understand how funding decisions are made and identify the opportunities for COIs to be integrated into that process, to help make some steps easier and/or more transparent.
- Find out what information fields on the prototype are helpful/not helpful, what is missing, and what replicates existing funders' tools from other sources, by having users engage with the prototype.

To gain a better sense of COIs' utility and potential use cases, Azizuddin conducted 12 semi-structured interviews with respondents from different types of institutions, ranging from philanthropic funders to academic institutions. Some respondents make long-term horizon, moonshot-type funding decisions, while others are very close to the use and implementation of these open infrastructure services in their communities (e.g. library leadership at a research university looking to implement a data repository service). Respondents included 8 global north participants, 4 global south participants, and among those 4 representatives each from philanthropic funding organizations, institutional decision makers, and national research and education networks (NRENs).

COIs has the potential to address several needs of open infrastructure funders and decision-makers. These interviews also identified some areas for further development and improvement that would enable COIs to address these needs.

1. **Open value education:** some respondents, particularly those at research networks and universities, mention spending significant time and energy on raising awareness of the existence of open infrastructure and educating their colleagues on the benefits that open infrastructure may bring. Including resources for basic information on open values such as community governance and open data as part of COIs may help bring third-party validation and help build overall credibility and trust for open infrastructure with those looking to fund, adopt, and potentially implement open infrastructure solutions. .
2. **Discovery and relationship building:** The current discovery process appears to be the least transparent part of the funding process. Respondents typically relied on relationships and word of mouth to find open infrastructure services to work with and fund; this advantages well-connected individuals and providers, and limits possibilities across the ecosystem. COIs can help improve the transparency and efficiency of the discovery process for open infrastructure, and also provide an opportunity for relationship building as it lists the names of services' governance members and current funders.
3. **Information transparency:** COIs may help level the playing field between funders with limited resources to conduct extensive due diligence processes and funders with their own analyst teams by increasing transparency. Some respondents mention that there are no generally accepted guidelines for evaluating different open infrastructure services. COIs' information and approach can help funders' analysis and make them better informed and more efficient.
4. **Providers and information sharing:** COIs' success depends on the participation of open infrastructure service providers. IOI should actively engage service providers in future research and development of COIs, such that we can promote the importance of transparency, incentivize

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/7152843>

service providers to spend time on ensuring their COIs entries are thorough and accurate, and build a community of COIs advocates for other providers. We also heard from decision makers the desire to be able to compare across services and/or data sources so that users can weigh attributes for similar services against their needs in a more streamlined fashion.

5. **Advocacy and sharing success:** The COIs prototype mostly tells a story of numbers, but the respondents also see the need to surface some of the narrative and untold story behind those numbers. By providing additional context on the information, COIs has the opportunity to provide a more thorough view of the open infrastructure services listed and use the additional narrative to advocate for increased investment in and adoption of open infrastructure. We anticipate doing this through adding additional analysis and/or data sources to illustrate uses for included infrastructure, financial runway, and shed light on robustness of the infrastructure's maintenance and technical architecture

The next phase of this work lies in further developing the utility, usability, and value of COIs into a fully functional web application with key features, functions, and information to serve as a central source of information on open infrastructure offerings and the organizations behind them. This application will meet the key needs we've identified and validated for better discovery, evaluation, and connection with open infrastructure services, including integration of additional analysis by the IOI research team, as well as examples of services in use to provide context to decision makers regarding the application and utility of a provider in practice. With this application, we will overcome the pervasive inequities in the funding system by addressing information asymmetries with a usable, informative, and engaging tool that enables more thoughtful and impactful decisions by all stakeholders interested in building more vibrant, viable, and sustainable open infrastructure services supporting research and scholarship.

In addition to the continued development of COIs, we also see a need to pair that work with targeted engagement and analysis on key funding prospects to further drive action from COIs and our research to resourcing and increased investment. In particular, we're keen to explore strategies to engage values-aligned for-profit companies in reinvesting revenue derived from open knowledge and open research activities back into the underlying open infrastructure and services that underpin knowledge production. We see organizations and companies that have pre-existing relationships with supporting open products, services, and communities as an initial area to explore, with additional criteria for examining values alignment to be designed with the support of IOI's Steering Committee and stakeholders. We also recognize that not all for-profits who derive value off of open tools, services, and knowledge production may be "values aligned" but may be candidates for contributing to a collective fund, which we would approach with care, transparency regarding our efforts, and enlist legal support to ensure proper safeguards are in place by way of term sheets and agreements. Beyond being a moral imperative on the part of commercial ventures earning a profit on top of these services, facilitating a return on the value open infrastructure services provide will also provide additional funding for these services beyond the existing institutional donations and grant-based support. We also view contributing back to be in the commercial vendor's best interest, as reliance on open source offerings also provides benefit for for-profit entities to have even stronger software to incorporate in their product offerings. We view a need to explore avenues that broaden and diversify the sources of funding and investment in open infrastructure, to assist in providing these services the financial support to continue delivering value for many decades to come. As with our COIs work, this work will be focused on reducing barriers through critical engagement to find viable solutions and actionable steps towards creating a vibrant, viable, and sustainable ecosystem of open infrastructure services.

We feel uniquely positioned for this work given our relationships with programs such as Anaconda Dividend⁶, a model for for-profit reinvestment in the Jupyter⁷ scientific computing ecosystem, FairOSS⁸, and our continued relationship with entities serving the research and scholarly ecosystems, from vendors and for-profit entities to institutions and funding organizations. In the 2022 Anaconda Dividend Report⁹, they note an increase in their second year of running the program, which started in 2021 with ambitions to

⁶ <https://www.anaconda.com/anaconda-dividend>

⁷ <https://jupyter.org/>

⁸ <https://faiross.org/>

⁹ https://know.anaconda.com/rs/387-XNW-688/images/ANA_2022DividendReport.pdf

dedicate \$25,000 USD to the community via NumFOCUS. In 2021, they exceeded that initial start goal by contributing \$44,735 back into the community, and in 2022, more than doubling that figure in donating a total of \$120,000 to NumFOCUS, in addition to the tens of millions of dollars they have invested over the past 10 years in creating, incubating, and supporting the maintenance of projects such as pandas, Bokeh, Jupyter, Dask, PyScript, Numba, and more.

4. Goals

The activities and outcomes for this grant build on strategic goals and objectives outlined in our 2021-2024 Strategic Plan¹⁰, which is appended to this proposal. We highlight the following goals below as especially relevant for the aims of this grant. Additional detail about how our proposed work will advance these goals and how we anticipate assessing the contribution of this work can be found below.

Those goals are:

- Increase our collective understanding of the funding and infrastructure landscape by conducting research;
- Further a shared agenda for investment in open infrastructure;
- Provide strategic support & investment guidance, to those looking to adopt, build, and sustain open infrastructure;
- Enable collective, coordinated action to pilot solutions and enact change;
- Build organizational capacity and effectiveness to deliver on our mission.

The proposed work to design, develop, and further scale COIs is a critical element to increasing our collective understanding of the funding and infrastructure landscape as an instantiation and public access point for our research on flows of capital, analysis on open infrastructure offerings in scholarship, and other trend analysis. Through the activities below, including ongoing research into core areas defined in our Funding Framework and input from our quarterly stakeholder calls, we will identify additional data sources to analyze and include in COIs, continue to advance our methods for analyzing and sharing insights on funding and provider data trends, needs, and current levels of investment.

We also seek to advance our aim to provide strategic support and investment guidance to those looking to adopt, build and sustain open infrastructure through COIs as a resource for funders and institutional leaders, and by conducting market research and targeted business analysis into aligned for-profits to assess commensurate giveback based on investments in and profits garnered from the open ecosystem. Our additional business analysis will support our efforts to model and test strategies for enlisting for-profit support in sustaining open infrastructure.

Underpinning the aims of this proposal is our ambition to further a shared agenda for investment in open infrastructure, to grow uptake and investment in open infrastructure by institutions and funders globally. A significant aspect of this work lies in coalition building and targeted outreach to institutions and funders to activate their interest, use of, and investment in open infrastructure. We see this work taking a number of forms, from stakeholder outreach and client support to grow the usage of COIs, technical work to improve the utility of COIs, and continued engagement with entities that can provide financial support to shared open infrastructure needs. This involves relationship management as well as improving COIs as a resource to increase the uptake and build market share of open infrastructure in institutional settings.

Lastly, we seek to build our organizational capacity and effectiveness to deliver on our mission by increasing our staffing specifically for COIs development and product, as well as engagement and relationship management support for open infrastructure providers. We will also be augmenting our current staffing structure with external contractors and professional services to move in a more agile and sustainable way, without increasing our long-term overhead significantly. With the legal and financial support, we also aim to ensure we're building models for contributions and funding that are sound, compliant, and with proper governance and safeguards to avoid undue influence and/or risk.

¹⁰ <https://investinopen.org/about/strategic-plan-2021-2024/>

We plan on assessing the contribution our work makes towards these goals through quarterly grant progress meetings, which we are beginning in January 2023. Areas we will be looking to monitor as indicators of progress include usage of and engagement with COIs, number of providers included in COIs, number of partners, expressions of interest and financial contributions to our collective fund, and additional insight from ongoing focus groups and assessments to check in on the value provided by COIs.

IOI is a fiscally sponsored project of Code for Science & Society (CS&S), a leading 501(c)3 that supports a portfolio of projects in the public interest technology and research sectors. CS&S is submitting this proposal on behalf of IOI and is committed to supporting the work of the IOI team to meet the goals listed above.

5. Activities

We are seeking support to develop COIs from an initial prototype to an integrated service that is more representative of the current open infrastructure landscape, provides actionable information that informs and empowers funders and institutions on where to direct resources, and is valued as a robust, reliable, dynamic offering.

In parallel to the continued development of COIs, we are also seeking support to model and test strategies inspired by efforts such as the Anaconda Dividend program, where for-profit and commercial entities that extract value from open services and labor contribute back a portion of their profits to the open infrastructure community to help advance open projects and their sustainability. We view this strategy as a critical and necessary step in increasing the overall investment and sustainability of open infrastructure providers serving the research and knowledge ecosystems. This also will build on the coming year's work to design, seed, and launch a collective fund¹¹ in 2024 to catalyze and deepen investment in under-resourced areas and expand the pool of funders of open infrastructure.

Below is a proposed schedule for major activities associated with this proposal. We have requested 21 months for this work to account for the hiring of a Product Lead and Open Source Community Manager and software development timelines.

Key activities for developing COIs include:

Recruitment & Hiring staff roles and contract professionals

- **Estimated:** late June 2023
 - Jobs posted: April 2023
 - Recruitment and hiring: April-mid-June 2023
 - Anticipated start date: late June 2023
- **Staffing:** Hiring search and recruitment for the Product Lead will be driven by IOI's Executive Director, Kaitlin Thaney, with support from the incoming Research Lead. The Open Source Community Manager search will be led by IOI's Engagement Lead Emmy Tsang and supported by our Executive Director and incoming Business Development & Partnerships Lead, whom this role will be working closely with. Additional scoping of work for contract professionals (especially for market research, software development, design support, and event design) are included as priorities during this timeframe as well. Additional Human Resources support to run the hiring process will be provided by Code for Science & Society staff and leadership.

Design a plan for developing a more robust application for the collection, storage, display, and maintenance of the information powering COIs.

- **Estimated:** June-September 2023
- **Staffing:** Led by Research Lead & Product Lead, with support from contract data, design, and software development support
- **Additional details:** The next phase of COIs includes a number of improvements, including further development of the user interface, overall functionality, security/reliability enhancements, and work to withstand growth and scaling of the service. In this activity, we'll be mapping out the details involved in building a self-service dashboard, admin panel, automated data ingest, and

¹¹ <https://investinopen.org/blog/ioi-launches-fund-to-deepen-investment-in-open-infrastructure/>

improved workflows for data curation and review. Accompanying this planning phase will also be discussions about the business model for COIs to ensure we're building in appropriate testing as we plan to launch the next phase of the service.

Implement usability and feature improvements to improve the operation and increase adoption of the application

- **Estimated:** September 2023 - February 2024
- **Staffing:** Led by Research Lead & Product Lead, with support from contract data, design, and software development support
- **Additional details:** Priorities for this phase include building a new web interface and self-service portal for submissions and review, backend security and reliability improvements, creation of an admin panel and curation tools, and development of user feedback mechanisms for continuous improvement.

Integrate additional information sources, including for the cultural heritage sector, via targeted data collection, analysis, and outreach.

- **Estimated:** September 2023 - December 2024
- **Staffing:** Led by the Research Lead and Product Lead, with support from the Open Source Community Manager, Engagement Lead, and contract research support
- **Additional details:** In addition to building out the technology to empower infrastructure providers to self-submit their data for review and inclusion in COIs, we anticipate a need to augment that work with targeted outreach and data collection to open infrastructure providers serving the cultural heritage sector and research community. We've already begun discussions with potential data partners, such as the Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative (COKI)¹² and the Research on Research Institute¹³ to enrich the information already available in COIs with additional statistics and performance measures that further enhance the value of the catalog entries in COIs. This can be done largely through automated processes and APIs that, once designed and built, reduce the burden on IOI staff while providing a better experience for COIs users. Additional data sources are currently being explored, especially as we look to further enhance the representation of infrastructure services in COIs. We will approach that discovery period for additional data partners through structured conversations with cultural heritage sector leaders, librarians and funders, as well as consult other references such as the Scholarly Communication Technology Catalog (SComCat)¹⁴ and data sources such as the CZ Software Mentions Dataset¹⁵ for learnings that we may apply to mapping infrastructure offerings serving research, scholarship, and the cultural heritage sector. We currently have a data engineer working on creating foreign data wrappers and ETL (extract, transform, load) workflows to enable efficient data ingest into our data store. More on this work can be seen in this presentation from August 2022 on database improvements.¹⁶

Streamlining automation for ongoing maintenance and testing of COIs.

- **Estimated:** December 2023 - December 2024
- **Staffing:** Research Lead, Product Lead
- **Additional details:** This phase will focus on building and planning for increased automation, monitoring, and reliability of COIs, including automated quality assurance and quality control checks, data backups and maintenance planning, as well as monitoring and development of automated feedback systems.

Create a sustainable growth strategy for the continued use and adoption of COIs that meets current and future user needs.

¹² <https://openknowledge.community/>

¹³ <https://www.researchonresearch.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.scomcat.net/>

¹⁵ <https://medium.com/czi-technology/new-data-reveals-the-hidden-impact-of-open-source-in-science-11cc4a16fea2>

¹⁶ Presentation by Matt Canute, data engineer, in Research & Strategy meeting (August 11, 2022): <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1V8Ew1cSD1OewOqaFLmNxS3FfLMz3F2megl2OvyoD4So/edit#slide=id.p>

- **Estimated:** July 2024-December 2024
 - **Staffing:** Product Lead, Research Lead, Business Development & Partnerships Lead, Executive Director, Engagement Lead
 - **Additional details:** Prioritized in this work is also addressing necessary cost recovery for the ongoing maintenance and operating costs of COIs as an application and service to stakeholders. While we want COIs to be as accessible as possible for as many potential users as we can, to ensure COIs is a valuable resource now and for the foreseeable future, we need to create a continual test and evaluation process to ensure COIs is meeting the needs of its users while also crafting a cost recovery strategy that provides on-going support for the application. This will ensure COIs is a valuable and reliable resource for many decades to come.
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Key activities for investigating the for-profit contribution model include:

Discovery for for-profit contribution model design

- **Estimated start:** April-May 2023
- **Staffing:** Led by Business Development and Partnerships Lead with support from Executive Director and Engagement Lead
- **Additional detail:** Initial conversations with a small group of value-aligned for-profits have already taken place. The Business Development and Partnerships Lead will follow up on the initial conversations to solicit formal interest in participation as well as look for and invite further for-profit entities into this work. This culminates in a virtual kick-off meeting in May 2023, organized by the Engagement Lead, where interested entities and IOI staff will gather to discuss and identify research and other needs to design and test this model in early 2024.

Market analysis and model research

- **Estimated start:** June 2023
- **Staffing:** Led by the Business Development and Partnerships Lead, with additional business analysis, legal and financial, and research team support where needed
- **Additional detail:** Based on the discovery phase's outcome, the Business Development and Partnerships Lead will work with the additional business analysis, legal and financial support as well as interested for-profits to research into existing contribution models, identify value propositions, and map requirements for commercial contributions to open infrastructure. This would involve analysis into existing contribution models (such as Anaconda Dividend and Corporate Social Responsibility frameworks), modeling potential contribution levels based on key criteria identified in the research, and conducting targeted analysis into value derived by certain stakeholders from open infrastructure and scholarship.

For-profit contribution model pilot development

- **Estimated start:** October 2023
- **Staffing:** Led by the Business Development and Partnerships Lead and the Engagement Lead, with additional legal and financial support where needed
- **Additional detail:** The Engagement Lead will lead the design of an in-person/virtual workshop, where the Business Development and Partnerships Lead will share the market analysis and model requirement gathering findings with interested for-profits for feedback. Together, the participants will brainstorm around a prototype model. After the workshop, the Business Development and Partnerships Lead will work with the interested for-profits to build out further details for the prototype and confirm a final list of for-profit entities that will contribute to the pilot.

For-profit contribution model pilot launch

- **Estimated start:** February 2024
- **Staffing:** Led by the Business Development and Partnerships Lead, with support from the Engagement Lead and additional legal and financial support where needed
- **Additional detail:** The Engagement Lead will lead the design of an in-person summit with pilot participants, where the Business Development and Partnerships Lead will share the latest design

for the commercial contribution pilot. Following this summit, the Business Development and Partnerships Lead will work with the participating for-profits to finalize their contribution and related terms.

Ongoing activities (duration of the grant):

The following are activities that we view as continuous over the course of this grant timeline. We envision these activities as ongoing tasks of the core IOI team with additional support as needed from contractors to augment and accelerate analysis, outreach, and integration into COIs.

Data collection, research & analysis. As we work to enrich COIs as an information source and explore additional dashboards for analysis, we will work to solicit additional data and context about the grants made from funding sources and data about open infrastructure providers, building on our initial prototype. We will also work to identify other publicly available datasets and service integrations (e.g. CHAOSS¹⁷ metrics and Cauldron.io¹⁸ to examine technical reliability and health of community) to augment existing data sources, such as classifications of institutions and organizations, institutional funding data (as it is made available/discoverable), in addition to the data collection and modeling work that is involved with the individual open infrastructure use cases.

Ongoing analysis and refinement. As we work to improve, deepen, and scale the utility of COIs, we expect the explorative nature of this work to involve continuous analysis as we work to add data sources and integrate our ongoing research. By “refinement”, we mean the work to standardize, tag, categorize, and summarize data sources before they’re used for advanced analytics. This work is noted as ongoing as in choosing to bring a data source online (for example, for the funder data dashboard), we are committing to make that data source available in a certain normalized format, consistent with our data model and usable for our analyses and that of the broader community.

Soliciting and incorporating community feedback. We aim to share this work out over the duration of this grant via quarterly Collaborator Calls, as well as through more focused community listening and feedback sessions to share findings, explore needs and challenges, and further iterate on our analysis and prototype. These stakeholders will be defined as part of the process following the selection of open infrastructure use cases and discussion of next steps for developing COIs as well as models and strategies to enlist for-profit contributions to open infrastructure.

Sharing out results on a regular basis via community calls, virtual feedback sessions, working papers, newsletters, and blog.

Development, consultation, and review for post-2024 IOI Strategic Plan. We will be undergoing the development of our next 3-year strategic plan during the course of this grant. This is listed as an ongoing activity as it feeds off of initial ongoing planning with IOI staff, done on a quarterly basis through pulse checks. We anticipate that the next draft will be shared with the IOI Steering Committee in January 2024, to begin a 3-month iteration process, followed by a 4-6 week community consultation, review, and posting on the website for late June/early July 2024, which marks the start of our fiscal year 2025.

Staffing plan

We introduce two additional staff lines (Product Lead, Open Source Community Manager) with benefits to support COIs development and growth in this proposal, with an anticipated start date of June 2023 (allotting for recruitment for those positions).

Resourcing for core IOI team members is noted as in-kind (due to being funded through Arcadia support) through October 2024 (when our current operational support from the Arcadia Fund concludes), with fractional support for all existing roles for November and December 2024 after our current operational funding is set to conclude. This is to help provide a longer runway for COIs development and testing, as well as to plan for IOI’s continued growth following the end of our Arcadia support. We are beginning

¹⁷ <https://chaoss.community/>

¹⁸ <https://cauldron.io/>

discussions with funders about post-Arcadia support, while also building out contributions for fee-for-service work and institutional contributions, which to date for 2023-2024 consist of commitments of \$335,000, with additional collaborations in early discussion that we estimate at totalling \$400,000 per year for two years. These commitments do not include potential renewals from funders such as Arcadia or others who have expressed interest in supporting IOI at a governmental level, such as the National Science Foundation.

Staff support in relation to this grant are outlined below (managing relationships noted below):

- Executive Director (Kaitlin Thaney)
 - Research Lead (*currently recruiting for at the time of submission - Jan 2023*)
 - Research Data Analysts (Tania Hernández Ortiz, Naomi Penfold)
 - Research Coordinator (Anne Britton)
 - Product Lead (to be hired)
 - Engagement Lead (Emmy Tsang)
 - Communications Associate (Jerry Sellanga)
 - Open Source Community Manager (to be hired)
 - Business Development & Partnerships Lead (*currently recruiting for at the time of submission - Dec 2022*)

The Executive Director, Business Development & Partnerships Lead, and Engagement Lead will oversee the identification of initial companies and organizations to engage in modeling a contribution mechanism to support and sustain open infrastructure. The Engagement Lead, with the support of the Communications Associate, will oversee the event design, facilitation, and execution of the kickoff meeting, mid-point working meeting and pilot launch, with additional facilitation and event management contract support. The Business Development & Partnerships lead will support the Executive Director in overseeing prospect research and preparing materials to support business development conversations as part of our effort to grow investment to open infrastructure.

The Research Lead will serve as the line manager and lead for hiring the Product Lead, and will work with that hire to design and staff with contractor support the development of COIs. The Research Lead also directs the work of the Research Data Analysts and Research Coordinator, who will continue to develop cutting-edge analysis for inclusion in COIs. The Open Source Community Manager, line managed by the Engagement Lead, will work closely with the Product Lead in building and maintaining a user and contributor community for COIs, to center community needs in COIs development and increase COIs's usability and value.

The Engagement Lead and Communications Associate are also key supports for the communication and sharing of research outputs. The Research Coordinator directly assists with the onboarding and offboarding of contractor support for the research team (which we anticipate for this grant will include software development, data, design, and research support) in addition to maintaining documentation in HackMD, deposit of research outputs in Zenodo and Dataverse, and categorization of reference material in Zotero. The Open Source Community Manager will lead on relationship management for the infrastructure provider community, managing requests, needs and opportunities as they relate to COIs development. They'll also work with Engagement, Product, and Business Development & Partnerships Lead to support growing the usage of COIs.

To provide additional agility and ability to scale without burdening ongoing staff costs we have structured resourcing for additional technical development, design, user experience, targeted research, and business analysis as contractor-level support. We also anticipate additional event design and facilitation support for in-person and hybrid events, legal and financial expertise as it relates to establishing models and agreements for contributions to a collective fund, and technical costs for cloud storage, database needs, and other associated services.

Collaborating partners

We also build on the existing momentum to incentivize for-profit reinvestment in open systems that underpin knowledge production, as seen with the Anaconda Dividend Program and initiatives like FairOSS, which both focus on corporate investments in open source. We anticipate engaging leaders of both initiatives in our research to model a mechanism and strategy to enlist for-profit contributions to collectively reinvest in shared open infrastructure needs. Additionally, we will continue to build and explore values-aligned collaborations and partnerships to further augment our research efforts, including with initiatives such as the Curtin Open Knowledge Institute (COKI), a hub for analysis and evaluation of open knowledge in higher education.

6. Sustainability

IOI is supported through a mix of philanthropic support and financial commitments from institutions and consortia-based organizations. Our current operations are supported predominantly via a 3-year \$3.4M grant from Arcadia, which covers the core salaries of our staff, administrative support, and some travel and convening support for targeted events. We are in our second year of that funding, which is currently set to conclude at the end of October 2024.

Our budget estimate below is based on an April 2023 - December 2024 timeline. Resourcing for core IOI team members is noted as in-kind (due to being funded through Arcadia support) through October 2024, with fractional support for November and December 2024 after the Arcadia support ends. This is to help provide a longer runway for COIs development and testing, as well as to plan for IOI's continued growth following the end of our Arcadia support.

With the additional support of this grant, we aim to gain better insight into the feasibility of COIs and our analysis providing sufficient enough value to our core stakeholders that we are able to offset the costs of ongoing development and staffing to maintain the service with paid supporters and customers. We are also building out our fee-for-service offerings, including funding to apply our research findings to practical improvements for infrastructure providers like 212c and the preprint server, arXiv. Current estimations for the next fiscal year for this work are \$325,000 USD.

In addition to exploring premium products and paying relationships for research and analysis surfaced through COIs and the fee-for-service model we're exploring, we are actively working to launch a collective funding mechanism, for which the for-profit modeling in this proposal plays a key role. There are a number of models we draw inspiration from who have augmented and offset their operational cost through various models where typically a 2 to 8% "management fee" is applied for administration of a collective fund, including initiatives such as Connect Humanity¹⁹, Open Collective Foundation²⁰ (who administer the pooled Digital Infrastructure Fund²¹), and New Media Ventures²², among others. While we anticipate that work ramping up over the next year, with commitments anticipated for early-to-mid 2024, we are keenly interested in how administration of a collective funding mechanism could help support our core research and operations costs, to lessen our dependence on grant-based support and integrate additional cost recovery mechanisms.

We will continue to grow IOI's funding and support via philanthropic contributions and institutional/consortial donations, the latter which we are framing as "Founding Circle" supporters. We also will be exploring government support over the next 18 months, which include ongoing conversations with agencies such as the National Science Foundation and others.

Organizationally, IOI is supported by our fiscal sponsor, Code for Science & Society, who in the event of a change in operations at IOI will ensure our core technologies and offerings are made publicly available. Over the next 18 months, we are also exploring timelines and needs regarding our long-term organizational status, especially as we enter into more complex financial mechanisms such as collective funds, which may dictate a timeline for incorporating as a stand alone 501(c)3 or explore a different

¹⁹ <https://connecthumanity.fund>

²⁰ <https://www.opencollective.foundation/>

²¹ <https://opencollective.com/di-grants>; <https://digitalinfrastructure.fund/>

²² <https://newmediaventures.org/investments>

non-profit structure. We will continue to update the Mellon Foundation and our core stakeholders as that exploration and discussion evolve.

7. Technology

The work outlined in this proposal will build on existing technical foundations created during the initial prototyping and launch phase for COIs dating back to 2021-22. As both advocates of open source solutions and believers in the transformative value of open source, IOI endeavors to leverage open solutions whenever possible. In line with this commitment, the existing COIs application is built largely using open source solutions, with the code hosted in a Github repository, as is common practice in open source software development. While the repository is currently private, we intend to make the source code and data openly available pending a security review to identify any potential vulnerabilities or privacy concerns.

The existing COIs application has two primary technology components: the backend data storage and frontend user-facing web application. Each of these components is outlined below, with more detailed documentation publicly available on our website²³.

Data Storage

In creating the COIs application, we manually collected publicly available data for the selected service providers and collated it into a spreadsheet that we uploaded into a PostgreSQL relational database management system²⁴ instance hosted on the Amazon Web Services (AWS) Relational Database Service (RDS)²⁵. PostgreSQL is one of the premier open source RDBMS, with extensive features, robust design, strong community support, and wide usage around the world in multiple applications. AWS RDS is an easy to use and cost effective service for quickly creating and easily maintaining database systems, particularly for small projects like COIs.

The initial data model was simple, built solely to power the web application we were developing to visualize the data, but in order to further develop the application, we are developing a normalized data model that offers greater flexibility to collect and store data to better support not only the COIs application but our larger research data needs.

To facilitate this, we are currently migrating the data store to a self-managed PostgreSQL RDBMS instance hosted on an AWS Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2)²⁶ virtual computing instance running the open source Linux²⁷-based Ubuntu operating system²⁸. The EC2 service is another robust, cost-effective, and widely used service powering technology projects at various scales, from small prototypes like COIs to large enterprise applications. Ubuntu is a robust technology in wide usage in similar applications with strong community and organizational support used in similar technology applications.

While this move to a self-managed virtual instance increases our maintenance requirements over the managed RDS instance, self-managing the PostgreSQL instance gives us the ability to build connections with external data sources through the use of foreign data wrappers (FDW)²⁹ not available through the AWS-managed RDS instance we originally used. These connections will enrich our store of available data and increase our analytical ability with a greater depth of information. Coupled with the data model redesign, we are building a data storage solution that will be able to power COIs and the research work of IOI for many years to come.

²³ <https://hackmd.io/@investinopen/COIs>

²⁴ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/PostgreSQL>

²⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Amazon_Relational_Database_Service

²⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Amazon_Elastic_Compute_Cloud

²⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Linux_kernel

²⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ubuntu>

²⁹ https://wiki.postgresql.org/wiki/Foreign_data_wrappers

Web Application

Working with a contract designer and web developer, we created a web application using the open source Django web framework³⁰ built on the open source Python programming language³¹. Django is one of the leading web development frameworks, powering a variety of websites globally. It is a powerful and robust framework for providing clean, responsive, and reliable web applications. Python is a widely used open source programming language with a vibrant development community dispersed around the world.

While based in Python, the COIs application incorporates the open source D3.js JavaScript data visualization library³² to generate some visual elements. Developed initially by developers working for the NY Times newspaper, the framework has become the default in web visualization, powering not only media sites, but various commercial and non-commercial applications with fast, readable visualizations of quantitative data. As one of the core technologies powering the global World Wide Web, JavaScript³³ is a robust, reliable, and widely used implementation of the open ECMAScript standard³⁴. Using web-standard tools ensures the COIs application will work as intended on virtually any browser anywhere in the world.

The COIs web application is hosted on a self-managed AWS Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2)³⁵ virtual computing instance running on the open source Linux-based Ubuntu operating system. This virtual instance acts as a web server³⁶, handling incoming requests to the catalog.investinopen.org subdomain and presenting the requested data to users. As stated above, the EC2 virtual instance is a robust, reliable, and cost-effective solution for technology projects such as COIs. While other hosting solutions exist, including self-hosting solutions, given the current size and resources of IOI, using a service such as Amazon Web Services allows us the flexibility to focus on building usable applications without having to take on additional operational overhead.

8. Potential Challenges

There are a few key factors that could affect the timely execution of grant activities and goals:

Recruitment and hiring (and rapid growth). This grant will provide resourcing for our first full-time technical and community hires. To mitigate any delay or disruption, we have built in an initial (2) months to our budget and plan for recruitment, and are exploring ways to maximize our desire for a shorter turnaround by working with recruiters. Additional time may be required to allow for a robust search. We also are in the process of recruiting for two leadership positions following the upcoming transition of our Director of Research & Strategy and hiring for a Business Development Lead. To support this rapid growth, we are exploring external support from a recruitment firm to ensure we are successfully hiring within our expected timeframes while also doing so with intention and an eye for equity and diversity, in line with our existing hiring practices.

We also are continually planning for staff attrition and turnover, which is natural for the size and age of our organization. To help minimize disruption in the case of staff turnover, we lean heavily on documentation and cross-training, as well as visibility on work products and processes via our weekly team meetings dedicated to pillars of IOI's work (e.g. business & operations, engagement, research & strategy).

Reluctance of for-profit entities to participate and/or contribute. We recognize that we may have reluctance and other roadblocks in our efforts to get buy-in from commercial companies to support open infrastructure financially. Additional contingency planning will be needed, building on our initial plans to target contacts that have showed signals of interest and readiness, as well as broadening our search to include a wider variety of contributors. We also will be reaching out to our foundation, non-profit, and institutional contacts for their participation in parallel with these efforts, in hopes of enlisting initial support to build trust and momentum.

³⁰ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Django_\(web_framework\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Django_(web_framework))

³¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Python_\(programming_language\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Python_(programming_language))

³² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/D3.js>

³³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JavaScript>

³⁴ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ECMAScript>

³⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Amazon_Elastic_Compute_Cloud

³⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Web_server

Risk of undue influence from commercial entities. One of the biggest concerns we hear when we speak about approaching for-profit entities for financial contributions to open initiatives is the risk of undue influence from entities looking to undermine the open ecosystem. We acknowledge those concerns and also believe it's necessary to outline with appropriate legal support mechanisms that enable means to engage with commercial entities to advance shared aims while still staying true to our values of openness and transparency. We have conducted deep analysis of governance models, have experts on staff from the nonprofit evaluation and management sector, and additionally have governance mechanisms of our own including a Financial Oversight Committee who we entrust to help guide us in this process.

Access to data on funding and budget spend for open infrastructure, especially outside of the US. Our initial work to gather and model available funder and provider data has given us a base for which we can build from. On the open infrastructure provider side, we are aware that public filings such as through Form 990s may not be available in the same form outside of the US, and recognize the additional research and engagement needed to ensure we are not biasing our offerings towards just US-based sources. We also know more intimately the challenges that exist in gathering, modeling, and analyzing funding and provider data, and are working on ways to mitigate those challenges through additional data modeling work and more dedicated outreach to data sources as well as designing a means for providers to self-submit their information for review directly via COIs.

We will continue to work with our network of institutional leads, funders, and infrastructure providers to outline approaches to solicit financial and resourcing data through collaborations with project leads and supporting organizations to the best extent possible so as to not hinder our research and analysis. We will also ensure that accessibility of data is part of our selection criteria for open infrastructure use cases.

Managing capacity amidst uncertain times. Over the past 18 months, we have seen capacity challenges due to ongoing effects of the global pandemic, illnesses, caregiving needs, and additional capacity concerns to our core staff as well as for our contractors. We know that the year ahead is one of immense growth (captured in this grant proposal as well as in our strategic plan) and are continuously tracking our staff and contractor's capacity to ensure deadlines are met in a humane, paced fashion. We are learning and iterating as we go, and have baked in regular check points on milestones and capacity needs to combat burnout, overwhelm, and missed deadlines. We will also work to plan for contingencies in the event of a disruption in staffing and/or resourcing where needed.

By the end of this grant, we expect to be poised to announce increased investment in open infrastructure with financial commitments in process from leading for-profit entities. We also aim to have "customers" and dedicated users of COIs who find value and utility in the information and analysis available in the service, delivered in ways that support increased adoption of open services and investment in shared infrastructures. This grant will provide IOI the resources to test out the willingness for companies who state their interest in open initiatives to invest in the underlying technology, infrastructure, and communities. It will also empower IOI to move our research efforts into a more applied state, incorporating additional data sources and analysis into COIs, and delivering that to our stakeholders as a product they find value and use in.